

Antitumour screening : The antitumour screening of the compounds 2 (sl. nos. 4, 5, 13, 16 and 27) were carried out at National Cancer Institute, USA, against Murine lymphocytic leukemia P-388 according to the standard method⁴ in BDF₁ mice. Ip administration of compounds began 24 h after the inoculation of 1×10^6 P-388 cells in BDF₁ mice and performed once daily for 1–7 days. Vehicle used was saline, saline with tween 80. The compounds were tested at dose levels 100, 200 and 400 mg/kg. The compounds did not show significant antitumour activity. The best T/C value (104%) shown as by compound sl. no. 13 (T/C \geq 120 is considered active).

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Synthesis of 5-(3,5-Dinitrophenyl)-3-[(substituted-amino)methyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione as Potential Biological Active Agents

Y. D. KULKARNI* and ALI ROWHANI

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University,
Lucknow-226 007

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THE oxadiazoles possess various biological activities¹. Hence, it was considered of interest to synthesise the title compounds and to evaluate their antibacterial and antiviral activities. 3,5-Dinitrophenylhydrazine was heated with carbon disulphide and potassium hydroxide in absolute alcohol to yield 5-(3,5-dinitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione (1), which was then subjected to Mannich reaction to yield 5-(3,5-dinitrophenyl)-3-[(substituted-amino)methyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-

thione (2). The biological activity of the compounds (2) was evaluated.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra were recorded using TMS as internal standard.

5-(3,5-Dinitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione (1) : It was prepared by the reported method².

5-(3,5-Dinitrophenyl)-3-(substituted-amino)methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione (2) : A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and formalin (0.02 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (25 ml) for 1 h. A secondary amine (0.01 mol) was then added to it and further refluxed for 4–6 h. The excess of ethanol was distilled off, cooled and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from methanol, (2; 50–60%); 2c: m.p. 245° (Found : C, 42.73 ; H, 3.80 ; N, 19.59. C₁₈H₁₃N₅O₆S calcd. for : C, 42.50 ; H, 3.54 ; N, 19.08%) ; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 645 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S), 1 590 (Ar), 1 300 (NO₂) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C phenyl) ; δ (CDCl₃) 2.38 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.1 (4H, m, CH₂NCH₂ of morpholine) and 7.2 (3H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds of the series were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (2)*

Compd. no.	NR	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
2a	Methylpiperazino	180	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₆ S
2b	Phenylpiperazino	210	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆ S
2c	Morpholino	245	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₆ S
2d	Piperidino	260	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₆ S
2e	Diethylamino	235	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₆ S
2f	Dimethylamino	120	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₆ S
2g	Pyrolidino	194	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₆ S
2h	Diphenylamino	140	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₆ S
2i	Succinimido	175	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₇ S
2j	Phthalimido	198	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₇ S

*Satisfactory C, H and N obtained for all compounds.

Biological activity : Antibacterial activity of the compounds was evaluated by agar plate diffusion technique³ against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* using tetracycline as standard. 2b was found to be most active while the others showed moderate activity. Antiviral activity was tested⁴ against *Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* (CT) for Sunnhemp Rosette virus (SRV). All the compounds exhibited activity in the range 30–63%.

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Flavonoids from Flowers of *Helichrysum buddleioides*

A. G. RAMACHANDRAN NAIR*, R. JAYAPRAKASAM
and

R. SIVAKUMAR

Department of Chemistry, Pondicherry University,
Jipmer Campus, Pondicherry-605 006

and

K. P. MADHUSUDANAN

Medicinal Chemistry Division, Central Drug Research Institute,
Lucknow-226 001

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HELICHRYSUM *buddleioides* DC. (Asteraceae), a small shrub, leaves thick, lanceolate, limb short, obtuse and flowers deep yellow in colour, is found in Babubudan Hills of Mysore, Nilgiris and Anamalais^{1,2}. The flowers of this plant are popularly called 'Everlasting flowers'. A number of *Helichrysum* species have been known to contain one or more of different types of flavonoids³⁻⁷. Some species have been recorded^{8,9} to possess antimicrobial and anticancer activity.

As a part of the continuing study of flavonoids of South Indian plants and in the absence of any record of work on this species, the flowers of *H. buddleioides* have been examined and the isolation and characterisation of three flavonoids, one flavone and two aurones, are reported here. The compounds identified are 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxyflavone (luteolin), 6,3',4'-trihydroxy-4-O- β -D-glucopyranosylaurone (cernuoside) and 6,3',4',5'-tetrahydroxy-4-O- β -D-glucopyranosylaurone (bractein).

Experimental

Fresh flowers (40 g) of *H. buddleioides* collected from the Nilgiris in Tamil Nadu, were refluxed with 90% ethanol and concentrated under reduced pressure. The aqueous alcoholic concentrate was processed for flavonoids adopting standard procedures¹⁰⁻¹². Ether and ethyl acetate fractions showing identical spots were mixed and kept in an ice-chest. The resulting yellow solid was separated into three homogenous fractions by preparative microcrystalline cellulose tlc (R_f of compound (A) 0.65, (B) 0.42, (C) 0.31; 50% HOAc). The three homogenous compounds were then crystallised from methanol and subjected to various tests including uv fluorescence and pc in different solvent system. Final structural determination was based on uv, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral analysis.

Compound-A: It was crystallised as pale yellow needles from MeOH, m.p. 328–30°; it gave yellow colour with NH₃, olive green with Fe³⁺ and red with Mg–HCl; purple under uv and yellow with uv/NH₃; λ_{max} (MeOH) 242sh, 253, 267, 291sh and 349; (NaOAc) 269, 326sh and 384; (NaOAc+H₂BO₃) 259, 301sh, 370 and 432sh; (NaOMe) 266sh, 329sh and 401; (AlCl₃): 274, 300sh, 328 and 426; (AlCl₃–HCl) 266sh, 275, 294sh, 355 and 385 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3400br, 2910, 1725, 1650, 1610, 1500, 1450, 1360, 1250, 1200, 1190, 950, 900, 850, 810 and 750 cm⁻¹. It was identified as 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy flavone (luteolin) by direct comparison with an authentic sample¹³.

Compound B: It revealed λ_{max} (MeOH) 262, 338 and 408; (NaOAc) 290, 338, 388sh and 462; (AlCl₃) 274, 321 and 436; (AlCl₃–HCl) 261, 339 and 408 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr (400 MHz, CDCl₃/CD₃OD, TMS as internal standard); δ 7.22 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-2'), 6.98 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2 Hz, H-6'), 6.60 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-5'), 6.42 (1H, s, =CH), 6.09 (1H, s, H-7), 6.02 (1H, s, H-5), 4.68 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-1' anomeric sugar proton) and 3.68–3.19 (six peaks integrating for six protons of glucose); m/z (EIMS, 70 eV) 286 (aglycone, M^+ , 100%), 268, 258, 153, 152, 137, 134, 125 and 124; FDMS 470 ($M+Na$)⁺, 449 ($M+H$)⁺ and 287 (aglycone+H)⁺; pc (Whatman 1, 28°, ascending, $R_f \times 100$) 10(H₂O), 14(15% HOAc), 54 (50% HOAc), 45(BAW), 54 (phenol) and 46 (t-BAW); acid hydrolysis (2N HCl, 100°, 2 h) gave aureusidin and D-glucose. It was identified as 6,3',4'-trihydroxy-4-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl aurone (cernuoside), earlier isolated from *Oxalis cernua*¹⁴.

Compound-C: It revealed λ_{max} (MeOH) 250, 267, 340sh, 389 and 406; (NaOAc) 285, 338, 386 and 455; (AlCl₃) 255, 287, 338sh and 446; (AlCl₃–HCl) 254, 273, 338sh, 389 and 406; ¹H nmr (400 MHz, CDCl₃/CD₃OD, TMS as internal standard) δ 6.71 (2H, s, H-2' and H-6'), 6.31 (1H, s, =CH), 6.04 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-7), 5.98 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-5), 4.66 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-1' anomeric sugar proton) and 3.65–3.17 (six peaks integrating for six protons of glucose); m/z (EIMS, 70 eV) 302 (aglycone, M^+ , 100%), 284, 274, 153, 152, 150, 134, 126, 125 and